

Anti-Colonial Colonialism of Revisionist Autocracies: How Russia and China Reaffirm Their Imperialist Identities

Introduction

Why are Russia's and China's colonial policies toward targeted nations—such as Ukrainians, Crimean Tatars, Uyghurs, and Tibetans—legitimized by anti-colonial and anti-Western discourses? This paper examines and compares the discourses through which Russia and China attempt to legitimize their policies toward both ethnic minorities within their borders and nations outside their control. The central focus is the anti-Western dimension of their colonialism, which targets both those considered by Russians and Chinese to be culturally proximate (e.g., Ukrainians in Ukraine, Chinese in Taiwan) and culturally alien (e.g., Crimean Tatars, Uyghurs and Tibetans) Others. The distinction between culturally proximate and alien Others—and the processes of “othering” reveal much about the ontological insecurities of authoritarian regimes, which perceive the West and its values as an existential threat to their power and legitimacy.

Accordingly, these regimes legitimize their imperialist and colonial policies through ideologically driven discourses about alleged Western neo-colonial plots, targeting both kinds of Others. This legitimization is grounded in imperialist identities that are simultaneously ideological and instrumental: authoritarian regimes justify their actions as securing an identity that is perceived as under threat from others, while defending themselves against significant others who endanger that identity. While Ukrainians and Taiwanese are framed as an inseparable part of core Russian and Han Chinese ethnic identity, Crimean Tatars, Tibetans, and Uyghurs are portrayed as part of more broadly defined Russian and Chinese civilizations that must be unconditionally loyal to the state ruled by Russians and Chinese.

In practice, such imperialist and colonial policies preclude more peaceful forms of coexistence, such as granting autonomy or adopting democratic governance. Instead, they justify military aggression, as seen in Russia's re-invasion of Ukraine and China's increasing aggression towards Taiwan, which could potentially escalate into full-scale invasion. Both states engage in internal and settler colonial practices. These actions are rationalized by a deep-seated anti-Western sentiment, portraying Russia and China as “forced” to act to prevent Western manipulation of these groups against their interests.

For the purposes of this study, colonialism is defined as “control by one power over a dependent area or people,” which involves subjugation, conquest, exploitation, and the

imposition of language and cultural values (Kohn and Reddy 2024). Colonialism is closely related to imperialism: while one can be an imperialist without being a colonizer, a colonizer is, by definition, an imperialist.

The article first frames Russia and China within existing debates on colonialism and introduces supranational imperialist identity, linking it to the concept of ontological (in)security. It then introduces the argument that colonial policies are legitimized as a means of reaffirming imperial identity through othering and blame-shifting towards alleged Western liberal neo-colonialism. The article subsequently presents empirical analysis of Russia and China, structured around culturally proximate Others (Ukrainians, Taiwanese, Hongkongers) and culturally alien Others (Crimean Tatars, Uyghurs, Tibetans), drawing on discursive analysis of official and semi-official sources.

Russia and China as Colonial Powers in the 21st century

Russia is repeatedly depicted in the academic literature as a colonial power exercising hierarchical domination, political subordination, and cultural erasure over its former imperial peripheries, including Ukraine (Oksamytna 2023, 2024; Durand 2022; Pedorenko 2022; Kotliuk 2023; Motyl 2024; Snyder 2022; Antelava 2024; Redbird and Homaniuk 2023; Makarychev and Medvedev 2024; Bossuyt, Amoris, and Riabchuk 2024; Kovalev 2024; Dickinson 2025; Beketova 2025; Kuzio 2023; von Hagen 2014; Morrison 2016; Kassymbekova and Marat 2022).

There is also an overwhelming agreement among scholars that the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) approach to peripheral regions of the People's Republic of China (PRC), especially Tibet and Xinjiang, can be understood as both settler and internal colonialist (Leibold 2024, Leibold and Dorjee, 2023; Ramanujan 2022; Byler 2021; Roberts 2020; Tynen 2020; Roche 2019; Anand 2019; Gladney 1998; Cosmo 1998; Kumar 2021).

Authoritarian regimes in Russia and China deny their own colonial endeavors and blame the 'collective West' as neo-colonialist exploiter. Therefore, these two autocracies must 'decolonize' the nations and countries from the alleged malign neo-colonial influence. The CCP refuses to label its policy as colonial by saying that its policy in Tibet and Xinjiang is not colonialist because these regions lie within China's historic territory, ignoring that assimilation, extraction and population engineering can take place within formal state borders (Elliott 2015: 209–210; Minde, Jentoft, Gaski, Midré 2008; Kolås and Thowsen 2005). Self-victimization is part of the policy of blame-shifting of these regimes. Putin's regime presents its country as a

victim of the West and as a self-proclaimed defender of historic Russian territory (Kassymbekova and Marat 2022).

Tlostanova (2008) coined the term “subaltern empire” explaining how Russia and other Eastern empires have pursued imperial, “civilizing” missions against peoples deemed culturally and racially inferior, while simultaneously being perceived as historically subjected to Western cultural, economic, military, and epistemological domination. They are thus both colonizers and subaltern actors—dominating others while also mimicking Western modernity (Tlostanova 2008). Despite some overlap, we provide alternative framework to the contemporary colonial policies of Russia and China because these regimes, unlike Western colonial powers, actively construct supranational imperial identities that are inclusive in form but hierarchical in function.

Non-Russian and non-Han groups are formally incorporated into a multiethnic “imperial family,” yet Russian or Han cultural dominance is maintained, portraying these civilizations as inherently threatened by the West (Callahan 2010; Leibold 2013; Shakya 1999). This identity-driven colonialism differs from the Western colonialism that, according to the subaltern empire concept, Russia is said to emulate. Contemporary Russia and China share construction of supranational imperialist identities through rejection of Western universalism and liberal democratic values, claims of moral or cultural superiority, and the legitimization of authoritarian governance as culturally authentic. Opposition to the liberal West is therefore central to these imperial identities. Both states also practice internal colonization—over Siberia, the Caucasus, Central Asia, Xinjiang, Tibet, peasantry from the same ethnic groups (Russian, Han Chinese) and minority populations (Etkind 2011; Leibold 2013; Clarke 2011).

Supranational Imperialist Identity and Ontological (In)Security of China and Russia

Since the core principles underlying the construction of supranational imperialist identities are similar, we can argue that Russia and China share analogous sources of ontological insecurity. Originating in psychoanalysis, the concept of ontological security pertains to maintaining a stable and coherent sense of the Self through autobiographical narratives and routinized practices. To be ontologically secure involves understanding one’s place in the world, knowing how to interact with Others, gaining recognition from them, and having a clearly defined role identity. Significant Others play a crucial role in sustaining ontological security, as they participate in routinized interactions and are expected to recognize the Self’s projected identity (Bossuyt, Amoris & Riabchuk 2024; Ejodus 2018; Narozhna 2022).

Ontological security suggests that states, including authoritarian regimes, act not only to ensure physical security (i.e., survival) but also to preserve a coherent self-image. States achieve ontological security by routinizing relationships with significant Others, developing attachments to these relationships (Mitzen 2006). Narrative frameworks help states reconcile concerns about identity, continuity, and self-image with foreign policy decisions that may otherwise appear purely instrumental or material. Narratives of heroism, victimhood, historical continuity, and destiny allow states to reinterpret past failures or traumas and align foreign policy with a stable sense of self (Subotić 2016).

This shapes countries' perception of threats, interactions with other states, and the structure of foreign policies. States require confidence in "who they are" within the international system. Threats are not solely military but may also be existential or identity-related. State actions are guided by narratives of selfhood, including historical memory, role conceptions, and cultural scripts. These identity narratives frame interests, legitimize policy choices, and influence responses to uncertainty. Challenges to a state's self-concept, such as threats to sovereignty, legitimacy, or cultural standing, can be as destabilizing as military threats, provoking identity-driven responses (Steele 2008).

For Russia, China, and other authoritarian regimes, ontological security entails maintaining a coherent narrative of legitimacy ("why we rule"), continuity in identity (e.g., as defenders of tradition, civilization, and sovereignty), predictable routines and symbols (rituals, ideology, historical myths), and control over internal and external threats that could destabilize this narrative. When that identity is challenged — by protests, opposition, ethnic autonomy, or Western criticism — regimes experience ontological insecurity and respond through repression (to reassert order and control), propaganda and myth-making (to reaffirm legitimacy), and military aggression to project strength and reaffirm identity (Kinnvall 2004; Rumelili 2015; Pardo Sauvageot 2025).

Colonialism as (Re-)Affirmation of Supranational Imperialist Identity

We argue that the colonial policies of China and Russia can be understood as strategies to cope with their ontological insecurities by addressing the sources of anxiety that generate such insecurities (von Essen and Danielson 2023). Our focus is not on identifying the instruments of these policies, but on their legitimization, which we conceptualize as the (re-)affirmation of supranational imperialist identities and compare across contemporary Russia and China. We identify this legitimization in two steps. First, imperialist identity is affirmed through othering,

which involves antagonistically denying the (culturally proximate) Other the very right to exist as an independent subjectivity outside of the supranational hierarchical order. We adopt a social constructivist understanding of identities, viewing them as articulated, dynamic, negotiated, and contingent rather than static or pre-given (Williams and Schwarz 2021).

Second, imperialist identity is re-affirmed by shifting blame onto “Western neo-colonialism”, which is depicted as subversive and threatening. The Other must be “re-colonized” by the imperial actor as a corrective measure, framed as liberation from Western neo-colonial manipulation. Colonial policy of subjugation is therefore defended as a defensive act, protecting the Other from the aggressive liberal West, which is seen as attempting to undermine the ontological security and superior imperial identity of the colonizers. Those nations labeled as “proxies” of the West must be subordinated and re-colonized to restore ontological security by preventing external manipulation. Once fully “de-colonized” in this sense, these groups can no longer be instrumentalized by the West against Russia or China.

The Self of Russia and China is constructed as a creator of a new world order within a holistic revisionist agenda directed against the core elements of the liberal international order. Both powers have turned to such revisionism because they perceive the principles of the Western international system as threatening to their ontological security (Groitzl 2023). In Russia, regime promotes alleged anti-imperialism and anti-colonialism, aimed against ‘neo-colonial’ policies of the Western countries in claims to unite the world under Russian leadership in order to liberate it from Western cultural colonialism. In the meantime, pro-regime public intellectuals, influencers and agitators embrace Russia’s imperialist identity. As pro-regime nationalist theorist Aleksandr Dugin said: ‘outside of empire, Russians lose their identity and disappear as a nation’ (Morson 2024).

We argue that Russia and China legitimize their colonial policies through blame-shifting to “Western neo-colonialism,” portraying Western liberal democratic universalist values as a neo-colonialist existential threat to their supranational imperialist identities (see Applebaum 2025). Liberalism and democratic values are seen as a tool of neocolonial domination, while Russia and China present themselves as the vanguard of global resistance against Western (neo-)colonialism. In Russia, this discursive turn of anti-colonial language at the official level gained momentum after Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022. Putin has repeatedly invoked colonial history to cast Russia as the vanguard of global decolonization. In his speeches immediately following the invasion, he expressed a sharp binary vision of the world order: ‘Either a country is independent, or it is a colony’ (Laruelle 2025).

In this logic, just as the West once colonized the world under the pretext of civilization, it now imposes values, such as liberal democracy, human rights, or LGBTQ+ acceptance, under the banner of humanitarianism and a rules-based order (Laruelle 2025). Liberalism has been characterized by regime's propaganda as the greatest enemy of the Russian world (Morson 2024). Similarly, Chinese official media portrays democracy and freedom promoted by the West as a new form of colonialism (Zhang and Qiu 2021). While the original form of imperialism have been territorial, Chinese discourses say, the current one is described as ideological, exercised through financial control, manipulation of the media, and influence in international organisations (Bai 2023). Human rights are depicted as “nothing but a slogan to cover up their [the West's] true intentions” (Huanqiu Shibao 2023).

Russia and China portray the West as hypocritical, claiming to champion democratic values and human rights while allegedly imposing its lifestyle, culture, and values on others—thus acting as the “true colonizers.” Both Russia and China advance discourses framing the West as attempting to transform them, two “unique state-civilizations,” into (semi-)colonies, while portraying themselves as defenders against Western neo-colonialism globally. From this perspective, populations in Ukraine, Xinjiang, Tibet are framed as being “colonized” or manipulated by the West, necessitating their (re-)colonization by Russia or China. This process is justified as protection and liberation, even when it involves brutal subjugation, assimilation, or cultural genocide. The regimes present these actions as morally necessary to safeguard both the imperial identity of the state and the welfare of the subjugated populations, who are depicted as unable to resist Western influence or recognize its alleged malign impact.

We conceptualize this strategy as *anti-colonial colonization*: the (re-)colonization of populations that are discursively framed as under the harmful (neo-)colonial influence of the West. These populations must be subjugated to reaffirm the imperialist identity of the colonizer and their potential as Western proxies must be neutralized. This logic legitimizes acts of extreme violence, cultural ‘reprogramming,’ and even genocide as defensive, emancipatory, or civilizing measures. Such colonial interventions are framed as protective acts against the Western “corruption” of the Other and as necessary for the survival and moral integrity of the imperial power.

Unlike classic preventive colonialism, such as Russia's 19th-century expansion into Central Asia to counter British influence, contemporary Russian and Chinese colonialism is identity-driven. It is not merely a strategic or defensive response but a means of affirming the imperialist Self vis-à-vis perceived Western threat. Both states present their domination as “anti-imperialist,” legitimizing it as protection and liberation from Western neo-colonialism

while simultaneously practicing systematic subjugation. This approach is closely linked to civilizational protectionism and sovereigntism, whereby Russia and China claim to defend their cultural or civilizational space from alien domination (Callahan 2010; Leibold 2013; Clarke 2011; Shakya 1999).

Resistance or refusal to submit to this imperial order by the targeted nations is framed as ‘evidence’ of malign Western neo-colonial influence, allowing these regimes to justify the subordination or assimilation of entire populations. Democratic values and external norms that challenge autocratic authority are depicted as Western liberal tools of manipulation, requiring decisive “decolonization” through authoritarian colonial intervention. This narrative reinforces the regimes’ self-perception as morally and culturally superior, legitimizing expansion and subjugation as protective acts rather than aggression.

Data and Methods

We have selected cases that illustrate the legitimization of anti-colonial colonization: Russia’s legitimization rhetoric towards Ukrainians in the occupied territories and China’s rhetoric towards Hong Kong and Taiwan, as culturally proximate Others; and Russia’s rhetoric towards Crimean Tatars in Crimea, and China’s rhetoric towards Tibetans and Uyghurs, as ‘culturally alien’ Others. We assume that the affirmation of imperialist identities vis-à-vis these groups will differ. These cases are considered the starkest examples of such policies by both powers since the 2000s, when regimes in both countries have become increasingly assertive (and repressive) in constructing supranational imperialist identities under the hierarchical dominance of their cultures.

Putin’s regime is particularly obsessed with Ukraine, emphasizing its subjugation, both internal and settler colonialism, and a return to “Russian roots” (Kolsto 2023; Shevtsova 2020; Kuzio 2023; Oksamytna 2023; Riabchuk 2016). Ukrainian emancipation from Russia is framed as impossible and unnecessary, as “true sovereignty of Ukraine is possible only in partnership with Russia” (Shevtsova 2022, 145). Similarly, the CCP presents Hong Kong and Taiwan as internal parts of the PRC, with local citizens being basically identical to Han Chinese. Both regions are framed as being under the attack of the West and in need China’s protection. In Hong Kong, China imposes colonial policies, attempting to eradicate alleged Western (primarily British) influence. Similarly, in the case of Taiwan, China legitimizes potential colonizing policies, following planned “re-unification”. Paradoxically, China frames these policies as “decolonization” (Yang 2022).

As culturally alien Others, Crimean Tatars have been subjected to settler and internal colonialism in Crimea since 2014, including the relocation of Russian citizens to alter the demographic balance (Nedyelko 2024; Mikhalevska 2024; Khalilova 2024). Crimean Tatars, who made up roughly 13 % of the population before 2014, have faced assimilation policies by the occupying forces. The Kremlin has sought to subjugate Crimean Tatars through a campaign of oppression aimed at erasing their history and asserting that the land has always been Russian. Any expression of Crimean Tatar identity, or even mild criticism of the authorities, is met with arbitrary arrest, torture, or imprisonment (Berg 2024; Aliev 2024; Charron 2020).

China's settler-colonial policies in Xinjiang have reached extreme levels over the past decade. As confirmed by the 2022 OHCHR report on the situation in the region, state policies have included cultural and religious restrictions such as the demolition of mosques, shrines, and cemeteries, the prohibition of the Uyghur language, large-scale detention and forced "re-education", forced birth control, and coercive labor transfers (OHCHR 2022). The harshest measures in Xinjiang began under Chen Quanguo, who moved there in 2016 after serving as the CCP secretary in Tibet. Similarly, in Tibet, China has been conducting expropriation of natural resources, massive state-sponsored migration of Han Chinese, extensive surveillance, and restrictions on culture, language, and religion (Chen, Miller and Shakespear 2024), as well as militarized "transformation" trainings (Zenz 2020).

The sources for this analysis were selected to reflect (semi-)official discourses in Russia and China. In this paper, we focused on discursive habitats in both states, defined as the combined work of state institutions and a constellation of institutional and individual ideological entrepreneurs - state officials, propagandists, and nonstate pro-regime hardliners (Laruelle 2023). We examined hundreds of Russian and Chinese (semi-)official sources - state officials, propagandists, and pro-regime nonstate actors who were particularly vocal on examined topics. After reading thousands of texts, 250 representative articles and posts were selected per each case, making it 500 in total, based on content and source relevance. The searches in both cases used keywords such as 'Western,' 'imperialist,' 'anti-China/anti-Russian forces,' 'neo-colonial,' and 'de-colonization.'

Chinese sources, state affiliated news media and official institutional websites reflecting official discourse, were identified through keyword searches on Baidu and on selected websites, including Global Times, the State Council, ChinaXinjiang.cn, and Tibet.cn. The selected sources were diverse, encompassing official and semi-official materials such as articles by senior academics affiliated with state institutions. However, all of the sources were published

in channels directly affiliated with or controlled by the CCP or the state, and given their focus on highly sensitive issues, it can be assumed that they represent the official stance.

In the case of Russia, data were collected from both official and unofficial sources, analyzing a wide range of actors, including state officials, political and public figures, and propagandists. The lion's share of the sources was scraped from several dozen pre-selected Telegram channels and official media outlets. Telegram enjoys mass popularity in Russia and is widely used by pro-regime non-state actors with large followings, playing an important role in Russia's information space (Pertsev 2023). Additional data sources include digests of Russian propaganda, such as *Russian Media Monitor* on YouTube.

The selection of all sources intentionally focuses on examples of legitimization of imperialist identity. It is illustrative rather than exhaustive, highlighting prominent voices in Russia's and China's information sphere. The discursive analysis in this paper identifies recurrent narratives through which colonial practices are legitimized. Focusing on recurring frames rather than individual texts allowed to understand the shared logics through which Russia and China construct and justify their supranational imperialist identities. Statements were grouped into two main sections, one focusing on the affirmation of supranational imperialist identities and the other on anti-Western decolonization through colonization. Each of these sections is further divided according to the type of Other addressed, distinguishing between culturally proximate and culturally alien groups.

Affirmation of Supranational Imperialist Identities towards the Others

Ukrainians, Hongkongers and Taiwanese have formed an independent identity — yet this is not accepted by the Chinese regime nor by the Russian one.

Culturally Proximate Others – Ukrainians, Hongkongers, and Taiwanese

According to surveys, around two thirds of Taiwan's citizens currently consider themselves primarily Taiwanese (Huang and Starr 2024). Taiwanese people have kept a distinct cultural identity, including the dominant use of traditional characters (rather than the simplified characters used in mainland China), and about two-thirds still reporting in 2024 daily use of local languages (Lin and Chung 2024). In Hong Kong, more than a third identified themselves primarily as Hongkongers in 2023 and more than half as both Hongkongers and Chinese

(Corichi and Huang 2024). Hongkongers also developed a distinct cultural identity, including the use of spoken Cantonese as well as traditional characters.

All selected culturally proximate Others (Ukrainians, Hongkongers, and Taiwanese) are considered “one nation” by the colonial powers. Russia articulates its Self as superior in relation to Ukraine by promoting a common Slavic authenticity, with Russians as the “big brothers” (Bossuyt, Amoris & Riabchuk 2024). In Russia, Ukrainians are historically and contemporarily depicted as ungrateful, backward, indolent, and inferior—thus in need of imperial guidance. It says that Ukrainians are unable to run something so complicated as the state and if they try to do it without Russia’s protectorate, they will eventually end up as puppet of Russia’s adversaries that intend to use Ukraine for its malicious plots (Oksamytna 2023; Ioffe 2023; Medvedev 2023).

Table 1: Affirmation of Supranational Imperialist Identities towards the Others

	<i>Culturally Proximate Other</i>	<i>Culturally Alien Other</i>
<i>Ethnic and Cultural Identity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peripheral part (culturally, geographically) of the ethnic core, “one nation.” - Ethnic identity as artificial, (co-)created by the West to be used as a tool against the imperial center (West as creator of both national identities and nationalist movements). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autonomous on the ethnic core but assimilated into broader civilizational and imperial hierarchy. - Ethnic identity is genuine but inherently disloyal and potentially manipulated by the West (West as creator of nationalist movements, not identities).
<i>‘De-colonization’</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restoration of ‘historical roots’ within a shared Slavic or Chinese cultural sphere. - ‘Neo-colonial occupation’ of people’s minds, often in tandem with nationalist elites of the targeted nation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration into the broader civilizational hierarchy to secure loyalty. - Prevention of the utilization of grievances of the targeted nation against the imperial center by the West

Russia affirms its supremacist imperialist identity by denying the existence of Ukrainian culture. Pro-regime film director Vladimir Bortko claims: “Ukrainian culture as such, independent, does not exist. It develops only together with Russian culture, as a part of it. Separate is nonsense. [...] As part of Russian culture, Ukrainian culture is very good”

(Nesterova 2023). Similarly, Sergei Markov, a former Putin’s advisor, stated: “[Ukrainians] were part of a highly developed civilization! [...] Ukraine with Russia flourishes; Ukraine without Russia turns to ruins” (Russian Media Monitor, 12 August 2023).

By contrast, the PRC frames Hongkongers and Taiwanese in moral rather than cultural supremacist terms. Given the claim of a single, identical nation, it is difficult to belittle them as inferior or backward. Instead, it is emphasized that they are influenced by harmful Western values and colonialist thinking, and thus in need of decolonization (Yang 2022). Their distinct identities are described as artificially created by the West (Global Times 2022).

In all these cases, however, expression of a separate identity is viewed as a direct challenge to Russia’s or China’s imperial identity by its rulers and a potential catalyst for the fragmentation of the Russian and Chinese state-civilization (Sapuppo 2023). Ukrainian independence is perceived as a diminishment of the Russian empire, weakening it. The loss of Ukraine is equated with the mutilation of the Russian body and soul, as if Russian imperialist identity cannot be complete without Ukrainians as part of it (Nicolosi 2022). Ukraine is central to the affirmation of Russia’s imperialist identity as core territory. Hong Kong and Taiwan are also integral to China’s imperial identity. In both cases, these territories are viewed as having been symbolically lost under Western pressure, and their reclamation is framed as a restoration of the empire.

Hong Kong was ceded to Britain under the unequal treaties that followed the Opium Wars and as such it has come to symbolise the Century of Humiliation. Its transfer to PRC administration is presented as a “return to the motherland” (Global Times 2022). Similarly as Hongkongers, the citizens of Taiwan are presented as “belonging to the same Chinese nation, sharing a common language, culture, history, traditions, customs and folkways” (Liu 2006). Although foreign forces are said to be working hard to undermine these links, the “umbilical cord of national, blood, and historical ties” cannot be “severed or broken” (Liu 2006).

Russia aims not only for the total subjugation of Ukraine under the “Russian world,” but also for the return of Ukrainian society to its alleged “Russian roots.” The end of the war is envisioned as the birth of a “new Ukrainian identity” based on the notion of Ukraine and Russia as a single nation (Pynnöniemi and Parpei 2024). Both regimes seek ‘re-education’ of these nations—in this context, it refers to the reconfiguration of their own identity by asserting that they are in fact someone else. They are expected to become identical to the colonizer, to adopt the colonizer’s identity and thereby strengthen it, reinforcing the colonizer’s self-conception by relinquishing their own (Vickers and Morris 2022; Chou 2024).

Pro-regime nationalist Pavel Kukhomirov told in the interview that “the modern Ukrainian state exists as a battering ram aimed against Russia. It has no other purpose for its existence. Since Ukrainians are Russians who were artificially forced into adopting ‘Ukrainianness’, their entire existence is geared toward being anti-Russian. As soon as Ukraine and Ukrainians cease to be the ‘anti-Russia,’ that is, cease to be actively and aggressively driven toward destroying Russia and everything Russian, they instantly become Russia and Russians themselves” (Yadocent 2025). Ukraine must be destroyed and Russified (“liberated from Ukrainian identity”) because it is incapable of being friendly or neutral (Syny monarchii, 14 January 2023). Petr Akopov, a Russian propagandist for RIA Novosti, stated: “The experiment of a separate Ukraine has been recognized as a failure [...] Not just unsuccessful, but dangerous for Russia” (Akopov 2022).

Hongkonger and Taiwanese identities are also regarded as potentially dangerous because they challenge the narrative of a unified Chinese nation and undermine the legitimacy of the PRC’s centralized, Sinicized order. The PRC government explicitly presents the Taiwan independence movement as a consequence of “external forces” that “condone and incite [...] separatist forces to stir up trouble and provocation” (State Council 2022). Foreign forces are depicted as exploiting Taiwan to constrain China's development: by “playing the ‘Taiwan card’”, they are “using Taiwan as a pawn to curb China's development and progress and obstruct the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation” (State Council 2022).

Culturally Alien Others – Crimean Tatars, Tibetans, and Uyghurs

In both China and Russia, imperial and national identity are structured around an ethnic core, the Han in China and ethnic Russians in Russia, positioned at the top of the hierarchy and regarded as bearing primary responsibility for providing guidance within the broader imperial civilization and hierarchy. This framework is inclusive in the sense that all groups are expected to adopt a Chinese or Russian civic and cultural identity, regardless of their distinct ethnic origins. As a result, individuals may possess a dual identity, maintaining their ethnic particularity while simultaneously being incorporated into a wider imperial entity.

The Han nationality, led by the CCP, is presented in a colonialist spirit as the bearer of civilization, development, and education, within a supranational imperialist concept of China with the dominant Han ethnic core within ‘inclusive’ concept of Chinese identity (Harrell 1996). According to the official discourse, there are no indigenous peoples in China, because “the concept of indigenous is used relative to external colonizers” and “China is a unified,

polyethnic state” (Elliott 2015: 209-210). China’s settler-colonial policies have reached extreme levels over the past decade in Xinjiang (OHCHR 2022). Labor programs targeting primarily rural minorities, involving centralized training and organized transfers to industrial factories, are presented as particularly beneficial for transforming the ‘backward’ thinking of ethnic minorities. Official sources recount stories of Uyghurs learning to use a flush toilet and shower (Xinhua 2020).

Tibetan and Uyghur nationalist movements are considered by China to be secessionist, extremist, or even terrorist. One of the common narratives is that the West is behind the emergence and rise of Tibetan and Uyghur nationalist movements (Zhang and Qiu 2021; Guli 2014). In other words, it suggests that without Western intervention, these movements would never have emerged or gained enough strength. Great Britain allegedly initiated the “Tibetan independence” movement, which is depicted as a product of imperialist aggression (Tongyi Luntan 2013).

Similarly, Britain allegedly deliberately spread Islamism and Turkism in Xinjiang (Guli Azati Tuerxun 2014). After the founding of the PRC, the United States were mainly responsible for the support of nationalist movements, described as “tools of the West” conducting subversive and violent activities to undermine China (CCTV Guoji Wangluo 2001). Narratives also stress that people supporting “separatist” ideas are only a “very small number” of individuals allegedly influenced by foreign forces, implying that without foreign interference, no resistance would exist (Guowuyuan Xinwen Bangongshi 2003).

Crimean Tatars have been considered disloyal to Russian/Soviet because of historical memory and experience with oppressive regimes since 18th century. The annexation of Crimea in 2014 became a direct continuation of previous persecution for the Crimean Tatars, including their genocidal deportation by Stalin in May 1944. The aim was to increase pressure on the Crimean Tatars, who had not been loyal to the Kremlin since the very beginning of the occupation of the peninsula in 2014 (Meduza 2023). Russian occupying authorities moved swiftly to stifle the distinctive culture and identity of the Crimean Tatars after the annexation. Most of Crimean Tatar NGOs, media outlets, and religious associations were forcibly shut down. The Russian authorities gradually pushed the Crimean Tatar language out of the education system and public life. The representative political body, the Mejlis, has been banned. The occupation authorities in Crimea show a blatant disregard for Crimean Tatar cultural heritage, identity, and memorial sites (Ukrainer 2025).

Anti-Western ‘De-Colonization’ through Proxy (Re-)Colonization

The next part of reaffirming the imperialist identities of China and Russia is the legitimization of their colonial enterprises as acts of “de-colonization” of peoples allegedly manipulated by the neo-colonial West, portrayed as the ultimate threat.

Culturally Proximate Others – Ukrainians, Taiwanese, and Hongkongers

Ukraine is portrayed by Russian propagandists as colonized by the “collective West,” acting as a proxy under Western guidance to wage war against Russia (Pynnöniemi and Parpei 2024; Shevtsova 2022, 145). Former Putin’s advisor Sergei Markov claims: “The territory of Ukraine must be liberated from the junta and the political occupation of the US and British intelligence services” (Logika Markova, 16 February 2023). Nikolai Starikov frames Ukraine’s sole purpose as serving as a tool against Russia (NTS Sevastopol 2019). Russia’s task is to “take Ukraine back where it belongs,” i.e., to unite it with Russia or reincorporate it as part of the Russian state. Russia’s war is thus legitimized as the “decolonization” of Ukraine from Anglo-Saxon colonialism, as argued by pro-regime Stalinist publicist Nikolai Starikov. This logic frames Russian colonization of Ukraine as a form of de-colonization. Aleksei Mukhin, a propagandist, states: “Ukraine is being sanitized in order to return it to sovereignty [...]. In fact, Russia is decolonizing its former Soviet partner. There is a return from colonial hell to the normal functioning of the (Ukrainian) country, state, and society” (Chernov 2022).

Russia and China present themselves as rescuers and saviors from the West. The neo-colonial ‘evil’ must be uprooted by Russia, capable of rescuing Ukraine from the West's ‘decadent temptations’ (Pynnöniemi and Parpei 2024). The “collective West” is depicted by Russian propaganda as the ultimate neo-colonial manipulator, “the architect, source, and sponsor of Ukrainian Nazism” (Sergeitsev 2022), used here as a pejorative label for Ukrainian national identity. Sergei Markov frames the situation as follows: “The occupation of Ukraine by Americans is the occupation of [...] people’s minds, with a forced change of identity! That’s why our special operation is not a war against Ukraine; this is a war of liberation of these unfortunate people from a terrorist occupation by a nation which is tormenting and killing them and us and is ready to kill all the rest!” (Russian Media Monitor, 12 August 2023).

The perception of existential threat differs between Russia and China. In China’s discourse, the West is portrayed as a manipulative actor attempting to neo-colonize populations through ideology to constrain China’s rise. In contrast, Russia depicts the West as a direct existential threat seeking to destroy Russia as a state and as a state-civilization, using Ukraine

as a proxy actor to undermine its foundational principles. Putin's former advisor, Sergei Markov, said in February 2022: Unfortunately, the West [...] became obsessed with the idea of overthrowing Vladimir Putin and bringing Russia under their control. For this purpose, a coup d'état was carried out in Ukraine: the legitimate government was toppled, a junta was installed, and through a policy of state terror it set out to build an 'anti-Russia' (Vandysheva 2022).

China claims that the United States and the United Kingdom stand behind the unrest in Hong Kong. While the United States supposedly use this to contain China, the United Kingdom is portrayed as unwilling to accept the loss of its colony. They are accused of exploiting "a small number of anti-China elites who had been colonized" to provoke a "color revolution" (Yang 2022). The Hong Konger identity is described as artificially created by "hostile forces inside and outside" through "two battlefields" of education and media. The PRC government now seeks a "return of minds" through education, regulations and security measures (Global Times 2022). Repression against the protests is presented as a necessary response to foreign forces and ultimately successful (Yang 2022).

Taiwan is linked to Hong Kong as a similar case that has long been controlled by foreign forces as a colony. While Hong Kong is presented as a successful case where external forces were suppressed and decolonisation is underway, Taiwan is portrayed as a place where this still needs to happen. Most people in Taiwan allegedly desire unification and "the long-standing unresolved Taiwan issue is primarily the result of foreign interference" (Zhongyang Zhengfu Zhu Gang Lianluo Ban 2014). The lack of de facto control of the PRC over Taiwan is blamed on the United States, which "has long been a barrier to the development of cross-strait relations" (Shan 2015).

In one interview in official media, a teacher from Taiwan criticises that Taiwanese children are "increasingly influenced by Western concepts like democracy, freedom, and human rights" (Xinhua 2024). In Chinese official media, a Taiwanese professor was cited that after "unification", it will be necessary to thoroughly decolonize and re-educate part of Taiwanese society, since "some people have a colonial mentality ingrained in their genes, comparable to the Hong Kong rioter". According to him, the CCP could draw on its "accumulated valuable experience" in Xinjiang and Tibet (Yang 2022). China's ambassador in France made a remark in August 2022, stating that "once China establishes control over Taiwan, a process of 're-education' of its population would follow" (Wang 2023).

Culturally Alien Others – Tibetans, Uyghurs, and Crimean Tatars

The West is depicted as a neo-colonial manipulator that instigates separatism and other subversive activities among culturally alien groups to weaken Russia and China. The tools employed for “de-colonizing” minds of local populations from culturally alien Others differ from culturally proximate Other, particularly in China, which implements brutal campaigns to suppress any expression of independent national identity among Tibetans and Uyghurs.

As elaborated in the section on supranational imperialist identities, the West has been described by the PRC as responsible for the creation of Tibetan and Uyghur nationalist movements, and the United States has been portrayed as the main instigator of separatism from the founding of the PRC to the present, with these efforts intensifying as the US seeks to disrupt China’s rise (Huanqiu Shibao 2023). The West has been allegedly even willing to support terrorism to to “infiltrate, sabotage, split, and subvert” China (Xinjiang Ribao 2008), with Western media being described as “accomplices of the terrorists and extremists” (Global Times 2019).

Tibetans and Uyghurs are framed as manipulated, ideologically infiltrated, and subverted by the West, and resistance among ethnically distinct groups is portrayed as orchestrated by the West. International responses, such as sanctions addressing anti-Uyghur repressions, are described as further evidence of Western “neo-imperialism” aimed at maintaining global hegemony (Bai 2023). Accusations of human rights violations are said to be “fabricated”, driven by a “sinister intention” to “Westernise, smear, and even split China” (Ding 2021). The supposed democracy and freedom are described as “nothing more than colonialism in new bottles” (Zhang and Qiu 2021).

In response to Western infiltration, repressive and forced assimilation colonial policies are defended. As one Chinese academic stated for official media, “we must now strike, using offence as defence”, “we must leverage the superiority of the Chinese system”, and “complete the Sinicization of religion”, which he emphasised as the “most core issue” (Zhang and Qiu 2021). Accusations against the West for supporting separatism are accompanied by the justification of China’s own propaganda and censorship as legitimate countermeasures. In this context, Xi Jinping was cited by CCP media as saying, “If we don’t occupy the propaganda and ideological front, others will” (Global Times 2019). China should not make any concessions to the West but instead harden its stance. The moment China shows weakness, the West will allegedly exploit it to undermine the country (Zhu 2014).

In the same way as Tibetans or Uyghurs in China, pro-regime discourse in Russia see external forces to destabilize the situation in Crimea by supporting Crimean Tatars through “the stimulation of nationalist sentiments, including the terrorist threat [...] the national-radical

group (Dzhemilev-Chubarov), essentially manipulating the national feelings of the Crimean Tatar people, with a focus on youth and the intelligentsia, in order to create, in addition to external pressure on Russian authorities, an internal hotspot of tension” (Usova 2015). Exile groups, as with Uyghurs and Tibetans, are seen as West’s instrument, such as those which moved to Kyiv (Mejlis), or World Congress of Crimean Tatars. It supposedly reflects how the Crimean issue is embedded in the West’s campaign of pressure on Russia. Through so-called ‘national-radicals’ and the Crimean Tatar diaspora worldwide, the West aims to give the Crimean Tatar issue a long-term political and legal orientation as a means of exerting pressure on Russia (Usova 2015).

It is supposed to be beneficial for these exile groups to ‘engage in Russophobic and anti-Russian propaganda.’ According to Crimean ‘political analyst’ Ivan Mezyukho, they “all know perfectly well what the truth is, but they say what is advantageous to their Western patrons” (Tsargrad 2021). Putin’s regime in Russia also predictably denies any discrimination measures used against Crimean Tatars and blame the West from disseminating such ‘unfounded rumors.’ Russian State Duma deputy Ruslan Balbek claimed that “the national factor is being actively used to discredit the status of Crimea [...] the Crimean Tatars have become hostages of Western propaganda aimed at launching information attacks against Russia” (Shatalova 2018).

Conclusion

The West is accused by Russia and China of using neo-colonial tools of subversion to disrupt their imperialist identities that are supposed to be asserted by (re-)colonization of targeted nations that don’t deserve their own agency. The West is supposedly not competing in the old-fashioned colonialism but colonize ‘minds’ of this people to subvert the foundations of authoritarian regimes. Today’s geopolitical competition often centers not just on military power but also identity, values, legitimacy, and narratives.

Both regimes portray the West as competing via values and rather than territorial expansion targets the imperialist identity of the regimes through alleged subversion of the significant Other producing ontological insecurity. Russia and China legitimize domination through the paradox of “anti-colonial colonization.” They frame their expansionary and assimilatory policies as defensive responses to Western neo-colonialism, thereby converting aggression into moral obligation. Ontological insecurity generated by the Western-led international system produces a revisionist self-conception: Russia and China portray

themselves as besieged state-civilizations whose survival depends on hierarchical subjugation of others.

Both regimes legitimize imperial expansion as defensive salvation by projecting the West as an existential neo-colonial threat. Colonial domination becomes a tool for reaffirming a supranational imperial self. Repression against dissenters is legitimized by presenting opposition not as originating within the community, but as infiltrated from outside, by foreign agents. Human rights, democracy, freedom and self-determination are presented as neo-colonial tools employed to undermine the sovereignty of Russia and China. Propaganda is thus framed as necessary countermeasures to foreign influence. Showing any weakness or making concessions to the West is seen as dangerous and likely to invite further subversion.

Toward culturally proximate others—Ukrainians for Russia, and Hongkongers and Taiwanese for China—both regimes affirm imperial identity by denying their agency and existence as separate identity. Their distinct identities are depicted as Western-engineered deviations that threaten the integrity of the (re-)colonizing state-civilization. Culturally alien others—Crimean Tatars in Russia and Uyghurs and Tibetans in China—are framed as backward, manipulable, and susceptible to Western subversion, which legitimizes harsh assimilationist policies.

In all cases, imperial legitimacy rests on portraying the West as the true colonizer. The affirmation of imperial identity follows a graded logic of domination: culturally proximate others are targeted primarily through symbolic and ideological colonization (identity redefinition, narrative erasure, and political subordination), while culturally alien others face material, demographic, and coercive colonialism. Yet the underlying justification is identical: both types of domination are framed as necessary “de-colonization” from Western influence. This legitimization transforms violent assimilation and territorial control into morally framed acts of protection, decolonization, and historical restoration.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Regional Development Fund project ‘Foreign Interference in The Context of Geopolitical and Technological Change’ (reg. no.: CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008692).

References

Akopov, P. 2022. Nastuplenie Rossii i novogo mira, RIA Novosti, 26 February (deleted victory editorial),
<https://web.archive.org/web/20220226051154/https://ria.ru/20220226/rossiya-1775162336.html>

Aliev, A. 2024. Under Russian Occupation, Crimean Tatars Face a Campaign of Erasure, *Open Society Foundations*, 10 May, <https://www.opensocietyfoundations.org/voices/under-russian-occupation-crimean-tatars-face-a-campaign-of-erasure>

Anand, D. 2019. Colonization with Chinese characteristics: politics of (in)security in Xinjiang and Tibet. *Central Asian Survey* 38, no. 1: 129–147.

Antelava, N. 2024. When sameness becomes a colonial tool of oppression, *Coda*, 14 June, <https://www.codastory.com/rewriting-history/russia-colonialism-georgia-ukraine/>

Applebaum, A. 2025. *Autocracy Inc.*, New York City: Vintage.

Bai, Fan. 2023. Si kai Meiguo shejiang e fa de xin diguozhuyi “huapi” [Tearing off the new imperialist ‘mask’ of US anti-Xinjiang legislation]. *Huanqiu Shibao* [Global Times], 24 August. http://views.ce.cn/view/ent/202308/24/t20230824_38684916.shtml

Beketova, E. 2025. Behind the Lines: Russia’s Struggle to Colonize Ukraine, *Center for European Policy Analysis*, 20 February, <https://cepa.org/article/behind-the-lines-russias-struggle-to-colonize-ukraine/>

Berg, N. 2024. “Ne federatsiya, a imperiya”. Krym posle otkaza Rossii zashchishchat’ menshenstva, *Radio Svoboda*, 28 January, <https://www.svoboda.org/a/ne-federatsiya-a-imperiya-krym-posle-otkaza-rossii-zaschischatj-menjshinstva/32791342.html>.

Bossuyt, F., Amoris, L., and Riabchuk, M. 2024. The subaltern strikes back, or how Ukraine is claiming agency from Russia and the European Union. *European Security* 33, no. 4: 644–664.

Byler, D. 2022. Why Xinjiang is an internal settler colony. *The Art of Life in Chinese Central Asia*, 17 March. <https://livingotherwise.com/2022/03/17/why-xinjiang-is-an-internal-settler-colony/>.

Callahan, W. A. 2010. *China: The Pessimist Nation*. Oxford University Press.

CCTV Guoji Wangluo [CCTV International] 2001. Zhuanjia pingshuo Dalai fang Tai [Experts comment on the Dalai Lama's visit to Taiwan]. 2 April.

<https://news.cntv.cn/lm/523/51/52578.html>.

Charron, A. 2020. Russia's Recolonization of Crimea, *Current History* 119 no. 819: 275-281.

Chen, D., Miller, J. A. and Shakespear, M. 2024. Critical Han studies through the lens of internal colonialism: China, Guangdong, and Hong Kong. *Critical Sociology* 50, no. 1: 141–163.

Chernov, A. 2023. Aleksei Mukhin: esli Rossiya dast slabinu, sanktsii ne zakonchitsya, *Gazeta.ru*, 26 April, <https://www.gazeta.ru/social/news/2022/04/26/17638118.shtml>.

China Daily (2019). Demonstrators betray hidden US hand behind HK protests: China Daily editorial, 8 September,

<https://global.chinadaily.com.cn/a/201909/08/WS5d75046fa310cf3e3556a5a8.html>

Chou C. L. 2024. Decolonizing the 'One China' Narrative: The Case of Taiwan. *The Historical Journal* 67, no. 1: 161-168.

Clarke, M. 2011. *Xinjiang and China's Rise in Central Asia*. London: Routledge

Corichi, M. and Huang, C. 2024. How people in Hong Kong view mainland China and their own identity. *Pew Research Center*, 5 December <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2023/12/05/how-people-in-hong-kong-view-mainland-china-and-their-own-identity/>

Cosmo, N. D. 1998. Qing Colonial Administration in Inner Asia. *The International History Review* 20, no. 2: 287–309.

Dickinson, P. 2025. Putin is ruthlessly erasing Ukrainian identity in Russian-occupied Ukraine, *Atlantic Council*, 20 March, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/putin-is-ruthlessly-erasing-ukrainian-identity-in-russian-occupied-ukraine/>

Ding, J. 2021. Commentary: the truth of Xinjiang's vocational training centers. *People's Daily*, 21 January. <https://en.people.cn/n3/2021/0121/c90000-9811737.html>

Durand, O. I. 2022. 'New Russia' and the Legacies of Settler Colonialism in Southern Ukraine, *Journal of Applied History* 4, no. 1-2: 58-75.

Ejdus, F., 2018. Critical situations, fundamental questions and ontological insecurity in world politics. *Journal of international relations and development* 21, no. 4: 883–908.

Elliott, M. 2015. The case of the missing indigene: debate over a 'second-generation' ethnic policy. *The China Journal* 73, pp. 1–30.

Eskandari S. 2023. Internal Colonialism in Iran: Gender and Resistance against the Islamic Regime. *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 55, no. 4: 739-743.

Etkind, A. 2011. *Internal Colonization: Russia's Imperial Experience*, Cambridge: Polity.

Gladney, D. C. 1998. Internal colonialism and the Uyghur nationality: Chinese nationalism and its subaltern subjects. *CEMOTI: Cahiers d'Études sur la Méditerranée Orientale et le monde Turco-Iranien*, 25, pp. 47–64.

Global Times. 2019. Why do Western media ignore China's documentary on Xinjiang? 7 December. www.globaltimes.cn/page/201912/1172581.shtml.

Global Times. 2022. Success of 'one country, two systems' lies in responsible attitude of central government: senior political advisor. 2 July. http://eng.chinamil.com.cn/2022special/2022-07/02/content_10168465.htm.

Groitzl G. 2023. *Russia, China and the Revisionist Assault on the Western Liberal International Order*, London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Guli Azati Tuerxun. 2014. “Dongtu” kongbu huodong de guoji yinsu ji yufang cuoshi [International factors behind ‘East Turkestan’ terrorist activities and preventive measures]. *Alabo Shijie Yanjiu* [Arab World Studies], no. 4.
https://mesi.shisu.edu.cn/_upload/article/1e/75/425867804eaba4547ad3d6a31a9c/cf9ed99a-10b2-4378-ae6b-e6cfb82dd2e5.pdf.

Guowuyuan Xinwen Bangongshi [State Council Information Office of the People’s Republic of China] (2003). *Xinjiang de lishi yu fazhan* [The history and development of Xinjiang]. May. *Zhongguo Wang* [China.org.cn].
http://www.scio.gov.cn/zfbps/ndhf/2003n/202207/t20220704_129875.html.

Harrell, Stevan (ed.). 1996. *Cultural encounters on China’s ethnic frontiers*. Seattle and London: University of Washington Press.

Huang, Christine and Kelsey Jo Starr. 2024. Most people in Taiwan see themselves as primarily Taiwanese; few say they’re primarily Chinese. Pew Research Center, 16 January.
<https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2024/01/16/most-people-in-taiwan-see-themselves-as-primarily-taiwanese-few-say-theyre-primarily-chinese/>.

Huanqiu Shibao [Global Times]. 2023. Zhe tiao tuiwen, baolu chu shijianlai CIA ganshe Xinjiang de zhenshi lishi [This tweet exposes the real history of CIA interference in Xinjiang over several decades]. *Zhongguo Qingnian Wang* [China Youth Online], 6 November.
https://news.youth.cn/gj/202311/t20231106_14890236.htm.

Khalilova, D. 2024. How has Crimea changed after 10 years of Russian occupation? *Kyiv Independent*, 24 February, <https://kyivindependent.com/image-draft-10-years-under-russian-occupation-how-does-life-in-crimea-look-like/>

Kinnvall, C. 2004. Globalization and Religious Nationalism: Self, Identity, and the Search for Ontological Security. *Political Psychology* 25, no. 5: 741–767.

Kohn, M. and Reddy, K. 2024. "Colonialism", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Summer 2024 Edition), Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2024/entries/colonialism/>

Kolås, Å. and Thowsen, M. P. 2005. *On the margins of Tibet: cultural survival on the Sino-Tibetan frontier*. Seattle and London: University of Washington Press.

Kotliuk, G. 2023. Colonization of minds: Ukraine between Russian colonialism and Western Orientalism, *Frontiers in Sociology*.

Kovalev, A. 2024. Russia's Invasion of Ukraine is an Ultraviolent Settler-Colonial Project, *Medium*, 1 July, https://medium.com/@alexey_kovalev/russias-invasion-of-ukraine-is-an-ultraviolent-settler-colonial-project-a2f3c1ff5873.

Kumar K. 2021. Colony and Empire, Colonialism and Imperialism: A Meaningful Distinction? *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 63, no. 2: 280–309.

Kuzio, T. 2023. Imperial nationalism as the driver behind Russia's invasion of Ukraine, *Nations and Nationalism* 29, no. 1: 30-38.

Laruelle, M. 2025. Double-talk: Russia's Variable Ideology. *Survival* 67, no. 6: 29–46.

Lee, K. and Yang, W. 2016. Old Taiwanese vs. new Taiwanese: exploring the generational difference of Taiwanese identity. *Taiwanese Political Science Review* 20, no. 2: 125–186. <https://www.tpsr.tw/en/paper/old-taiwanese-vs-new-taiwanese-exploring-generational-difference-taiwanese-identity>

Leibold, J. 2013. Ethnic Policy in China: Is Reform Inevitable? *East-West Center Policy Studies* 68.

Leibold, J. 2024. The Tibet-Aid Project and settler colonialism in China's borderlands. *Made in China Journal*, China Columns, 12 November. <https://madeinchinajournal.com/2024/11/12/the-tibet-aid-project-and-settler-colonialism-in-chinas-borderlands>.

Leibold, J. and Dorjee, T. 2024. Learning to be Chinese: colonial-style boarding schools on the Tibetan plateau. *Comparative Education* 60, no. 1: 118–137.

Lin, R. and Chung, J. 2024. Majority feel ‘native’ languages are disappearing: poll. *Taipei Times*, 31 March, <https://www.taipeitimes.com/News/front/archives/2024/03/31/2003815723>

Liu, W. 2006. “Taidu” shili caonong “zhumin zijue” weibei guoji fa qipian minzhong [‘Taiwan independence’ forces manipulate ‘resident self-determination’ in violation of international law and deceive the public]. *ChinaTaiwan.org*, 29 August.
http://www.chinataiwan.cn/plzhx/zhjzhl/zhjft/200708/t20070801_425862.htm

Logika Markova, *Telegram*, 16 February 2023, <https://t.me/logikamarkova/5389>

Makarychev, A. and Medvedev, S. 2024. *Biopower in Putin’s Russia: From Taking Care to Taking Lives*, Budapest: Central European University Press.

Meduza. 2023. ‘Opravlyayut na voynu protiv rodnoi strany,’ 19 February,
<https://amp.meduza.io/feature/2023/02/20/otpravlyayut-na-voynu-protiv-rodnoy-strany>

Medvedev, S. 2023. *A War Made in Russia*. Cambridge: Polity.

Mikhalevska, K. 2024. Konfiskatsiya kvartyr i pilhy dlya kolonistiv: yak Rosiya zminyuye etnichnyi sklad okupovanykh terytoriy Ukrainy, LB.ua, 4 June,
https://lb.ua/news/2024/06/04/616769_konfiskatsiya_kvartir_i_pilgi.html

Minde, H. (ed.). 2008. *Indigenous peoples: self-determination, knowledge, indigeneity*. Delft: Eburon.

Mitzen, J. 2006. Ontological Security in World Politics: State Identity and the Security Dilemma. *European Journal of International Relations* 12, no. 3: 341-370.

Morrison, A. 2016. *Russian settler colonialism*, In.: Cavanagh, E., & Veracini, L. (Eds.). *The Routledge Handbook of the History of Settler Colonialism* (1st ed.). Routledge.

Morson, G. S. 2024. Russian Exceptionalism, *The New York Review*, 22 February, <https://www.nybooks.com/articles/2024/02/22/russian-exceptionalism-foundations-of-eurasianism/>

Motyl, A. 2024. Rooting Out Russian Colonization from Ukraine, *Center for European Policy Analysis*, 1 May, <https://cepa.org/article/rooting-out-russian-colonization-from-ukraine/>

Narozhna, T., 2022. Misrecognition, ontological security and state foreign policy: the case of post-Soviet Russia. *Australian Journal of International Affairs* 76, no. 1: 76–97.

Nedyelko, N. 2024. “Velykyi okupatsynyi korpus”: Rosiya zaminyuye naselelnya okupovanykh terytoriy svoiim? *Radio Svoboda*, 7 March, <https://www.radiosvoboda.org/a/rosiyski-zarobitchany-na-okupovanykh/32841005.html>.

Nesterova, M. 2023. Rezhisser Vladimir Bortko: Dlya menya net raznitsy mezhdou Novgorodom i Kiyevom, my vozvrashchayem vse, *Ukraina.ru*, 13 February, <https://ukraina.ru/20230213/1043506427.html>.

Neumann, I.B. 1999. *Uses of the Other: The East in European Identity Formation*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Nicolosi, R. 2022. Paranoia, Resentment, and Reenactment: The Russian Political Discourse on the War in Ukraine, *Ab Imperio* 3, pp. 247-261.

NTS Sevastopol 2019. Ukraina zatochena tol'ko na protivodeistvie Rossii (Nikolai Starikov), 8 August, <https://youtu.be/bObTnjPF7KY?si=sqmEDKO9M3TPpfYg>.

Ochonu, M. E. 2014. *Colonialism by Proxy: Hausa Imperial Agents and Middle Belt Consciousness in Nigeria*, Indiana University Press.

Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). 2022. OHCHR assessment of human rights concerns in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region, People's Republic of China. Geneva: UN, 31 August.

<https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/countries/2022-08-31/22-08-31-final-assesment.pdf>.

Oksamytna, K. 2023. Imperialism, supremacy, and the Russian invasion of Ukraine, *Contemporary Security Policy* 44, no. 4: 497-512.

Outlook China. 2010. Lasa baoluan [The Lhasa riots]. *Wenhua Zhongguo*, no. 62, 10 December. <http://www.outlookchina.net/html/news/201012/1471.html>.

Pardo Sauvageot, E. 2025. Russia's ontological security in the face of the Euromaidan: managing anxiety and overcoming paralysis through alternative ontological vectors. *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 1–24.

Pedorenko, M. 2022. History of Genocides and Inferiority Syndrome. What Is Colonialism — The Cornerstone of Relations between Ukraine and Russia, *Zaborona*, 9 December, <https://zaborona.com/en/what-is-colonialism-the-cornerstone-of-relations-between-ukraine-and-russia/>

Pertsev, A. 2023. "Russia's Broken Television." *Riddle*. July 25. <https://ridl.io/russia-s-broken-television/>

Pynnöniemi, K., and Parpei, K. 2024. Understanding Russia's war against Ukraine: Political, eschatological and cataclysmic dimensions. *Journal of Strategic Studies* 47, no. 6–7: 832–859.

Ramanujan, S. 2022. Reclaiming the Land of the Snows: analysing Chinese settler colonialism in Tibet. *Columbia Journal of Asia* 1, no. 2

Redbird, B. and Homaniuk, M. 2023. What Ukraine Teaches Us about Colonization, *Footnotes* 51, no. 1.

Riabchuk, M. 2016. Ukrainians as Russia's negative 'other': History comes full circle. *Communist and Post-Communist Studies* 49. no. 1: 75–85.

Roberts, S. R. 2021. *The war on the Uyghurs: China's campaign against Xinjiang's Muslims*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.

Roche, G. 2019. Articulating language oppression: colonialism, colonality and the erasure of Tibet's minority languages. *Patterns of Prejudice* 53. no. 5: 487–514.

Rumelili, B. 2025. *Conflict Resolution and Ontological Security: Peace Anxieties*. London: Routledge.

Sand, J. 2014. Subaltern Imperialists: The New Historiography of the Japanese Empire, *Past & Present* 225, no. 1: 273–288.

Sapuppo, M. 2023. Putin's Russia is trapped in genocidal denial over Ukrainian independence, *Atlantic Council*, 23 August, <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/putins-russia-is-trapped-in-genocidal-denial-over-ukrainian-independence/>.

Sergeitsev, T. 2022. Chto Rossiya dolzhna sdelat' s Ukrainoi, *RIA Novosti*, 3 April, <https://ria.ru/20220403/ukraina-1781469605.html>

Shakya, T. 1999. *The Dragon in the Land of Snows*. Columbia University Press.

Shan, Y. 2015. Meiguo shi zhiyue liang'an guanxi fazhan de zhang'ai [The United States is an obstacle to the development of cross-strait relations]. *Huanqiu Shibao* [Global Times], 20 July. http://tyh.taiwan.cn/luntanhuicui/201507/t20150720_10293437.htm

Shatalova, D. 2018. Inostrannye zhurnalisty sobralis' v Krymu, chtoby razveivat' mify Zapada, *Tass*, 24 April, <https://tass.ru/v-strane/5151291>.

Shevtsova, M. 2022. Looking for Stepan Bandera: The Myth of Ukrainian Nationalism and the Russian 'Special Operation,' *Central European Journal of International and Security Studies* 16, no. 3: 132-150.

Snyder, T. 2022. The War in Ukraine is a Colonial War, *The New Yorker*, 28 April, <https://www.newyorker.com/news/essay/the-war-in-ukraine-is-a-colonial-war>

State Council 2022. Taiwan wenti yu xin shidai Zhongguo tongyi shiye [The Taiwan question and China's reunification in the new era]. Beijing, August. https://www.mfa.gov.cn/ziliao_674904/zt_674979/dnzt_674981/qtzt/twwt/twwtbps/202208/t20220810_10738763.html.

Steele, B.J. 2008. *Ontological Security in International Relations: Self-Identity and the IR State*, London: Routledge.

Subotić, J. 2016. Narrative, Ontological Security, and Foreign Policy Change, *Foreign Policy Analysis* 12, no. 4: 610–627.

Syny monarkhii. 2023. Telegram, January 14. <https://t.me/SonOfMonarchy/8631> .

Tlostanova, M. 2008. The Imperial-Colonial Chronotope: Istanbul–Baku–Khujand–Moscow,” *Cultural Studies* 22, no. 2–3: 418–436.

Tongyi Luntan [Unification Forum]. 2013. Xifang lieqiang he diguozhuyi shili dui woguo de qinlue shi “Xizang wenti” chansheng de genben yuanyin [Western powers’ and imperialist forces’ aggression against China is the fundamental cause of the ‘Tibet issue’]. 23 June. http://www.zhongguotongcuhui.org.cn/tylt/20130603/201307/t20130701_4391104.html.

Tsargrad. 2021. Krymskie tatory na sluzhbe Rossii – razvenchaniye vrazheskikh mifov, 17 March, https://tsargrad.tv/articles/krymskie-tatory-na-sluzhbe-rossii-razvenchanie-vrazheskih-mifov-2_333927

Tynen, S. 2020. Dispossession and displacement of migrant workers: the impact of state terror and economic development on Uyghurs in urban Xinjiang. *Central Asian Survey* 39. no. 3: 303–323.

Ukrainer. 2025. Genocide of the Crimean Tatars: an ongoing crime, 27 March, <https://www.ukrainer.net/en/genocide-of-the-crimean-tatars/> .

Usova, L. 2015. Kak i pochemu izmenilas taktika Zapada v otnoshenii krymskikh tatar, *Rossiyskiy institut strategicheskikh issledovaniy*, 28 September, <https://www.riss.ru/news/analysis/kak-i-pochemu-izmenyalas-taktika-zapada-v-otnoshenii-krymskikh-tatar/>

Vandysheva, O. 2022. “Budut antifashistskiye vosstaniya”: Sergei Markov o planakh Rossii v konflikte s Ukrainoi, *Biznes Online*, 25 February 2022, <https://www.business-gazeta.ru/article/540893>

Vickers, E., and Morris, P. 2022. Accelerating Hong Kong’s reeducation: ‘mainlandisation’, securitisation and the 2020 National Security Law. *Comparative Education* 58, no. 2, 187–205.

von Essen, H. and Danielson, A. 2023. A Typology of Ontological Insecurity Mechanisms: Russia's Military Engagement in Syria, *International Studies Review* 25 no. 2.

von Hagen, M. 2014. *From Imperial Russia to Colonial Ukraine*. In: Healy, R., Lago, E.D. (eds) *The Shadow of Colonialism on Europe’s Modern Past*. Cambridge Imperial and Post-Colonial Studies Series. Palgrave Macmillan, London.

Wang, Szu-wei. 2023. Lessons for Europe from Lu Shaye’s controversial interview. *Prospects & Perspectives*, no. 25, 9 May. <https://www.pf.org.tw/tw/pfch/13-10069.html>.

Williams, P. and Schwarz, K. C. 2021. eds. *Studies on the Social Construction of Identity and Authenticity*, London: Routledge.

Xinhua. 2020. Baituo le pinkun, guo shang le xiandai shenghuo, weilai chongman xiwang: Xinjiang ji yuangong tan waichu wugong shenghuo [‘Get rid of poverty, live a modern life, and the future is full of hope’: Xinjiang labourers talk about life working outside]. 6 June. http://web.archive.org/web/20210208150257/http://www.xj.xinhuanet.com/2020-06/10/c_1126098148.htm

Xinhua. 2024. Zhi qi nan wei er wei zhi: fang tong pi “qu Zhongguohua” kegang de Taiwan jiaoshi Qu Guizhi [Knowing it is difficult yet doing it anyway: interview with Taiwanese teacher Qu Guizhi, who strongly criticises the ‘de-Sinicisation’ curriculum]. *Xinhua wang* [Xinhua Net], 2 February.

<https://www.news.cn/tw/20240202/1ccaa36509de42d49600cec11891a278/c.html>.

Xinjiang Ribao. 2008. Xinjiang zizhiqiu zhuxi xi jinqi baoli shijian, cheng xingshi yiran yanjun [Xinjiang regional chairman analyses recent violent incidents, says the situation remains severe]. 12 September. Reproduced on CCTV.com.

https://news.cctv.com/china/20080912/100803_1.shtml.

Yadocent. 2025. Pavel Kukhomirov. Memuar o nachale Russkoi Vesny, 7 May, Livejournal, <https://yadocent.livejournal.com/1795254.html>

Yang, K. 2022. Liang’an tongyi hou Taiwan zhili taolun zhi yiyi [The significance of discussions on Taiwan governance after cross-strait unification]. *Zhongguo Pinglun Tongxunshe* [China Review News Agency], 18 April.

<https://hk.crntt.com/doc/1063/1/0/9/106310994.html>.

Zenz, A. 2020. Xinjiang’s system of militarized vocational training comes to Tibet, *Jamestown Foundation*, 22 September. <https://jamestown.org/jamestown-early-warning-brief-xinjiangs-system-of-militarized-vocational-training-comes-to-tibet>.

Zenz, A. 2021. Coercive labor and forced displacement in Xinjiang’s cross-regional labor transfer program. *Jamestown Foundation*, 2 March. <https://jamestown.org/coercive-labor-and-forced-displacement-in-xinjiangs-cross-regional-labor-transfer-program/>.

Zhang, W. and Qiu, W. 2021. Zhe jiu shi Zhongguo: zenme jianghao Xinjiang gushi? Yong “jiangwei daji” [This Is China: how to tell the Xinjiang story well? Using ‘dimensionality reduction strikes’]. *Dixian Siwei* [Bottom-Line Thinking], 24 October.

https://m.thepaper.cn/baijiahao_15051193.

Zhongyang Zhengfu Zhu Gang Lianluo Ban [Liaison Office of the Central People’s Government in Hong Kong]. 2014. Yige Zhongguo yuanze [One China principle]. Excerpt

from Yige Zhongguo de yuanze yu Taiwan wenti [The one China principle and the Taiwan question]. http://big5.locpg.gov.cn/zggq/2014-01/04/c_125956428.htm

Zhu, W. 2014. Xifang weihe zai she Zang she Jiang wenti shang yu Zhongguo guo bu qu [Why the West cannot get along with China on Tibet and Xinjiang related issues]. Zhongguo Xizang Wang [China Tibet Online], 19 February.

<https://cpc.people.com.cn/BIG5/n/2014/0219/c64102-24406018-6.html>.

Zhuo, C. 2022. Success of 'one country, two systems' lies in responsible attitude of central govt: senior political advisor, Global Times, 2 July,

http://eng.chinamil.com.cn/2022special/2022-07/02/content_10168465.htm.